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Artists Attitude To Art Practice

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ABSTRACT

In Nigeria, most practicing Artist exhibit different character and behaviour towards art practice. In spite of the years, some of them put in for the training, they still abandon Art and go for other professions basically because impatience and some other flimsy excuses. This paper is basically concerned with the general attitude of artists in their art practices. From the findings, so many practicing and well trained artists have left the profession and run after politics and so many other means of getting money. The paper concludes by identifying some of the causes of dropout and further recommends that professionalism should be encouraged in Art practice.

Keywords: Art practice, Attitude, Drop out

INTRODUCTION

Many Scholars have attempted to define art. For instance, Lawal-Ojibara (2007) defines art as a way in which man expresses his feelings, perceptions and thoughts about himself or the world of people and nature. He further states that some people attempt to produce what their eyes see, others prefer to express only personal feelings. He also maintains that when we utilize paint or any other relevant medium to express or depict what we feel or see in a manner that affects the sense of beauty we are creating art.

Another interesting definition was offered by Talabi (1979) and Ganagana (2000:1) which state that "Art is the creation or reproduction of ideas, thought and imagination into visual and practical reality from shamble and chaos. This involves creation of a specific order, rhythm, balance and proportion. The later argued that art as generally known is talent, which involves exploration, invention, discovery of the visual world and creativity from the real and beyond the real. Talented artist explores different materials in order to discover new knowledge which brings about innovation into his work. He does that either through imagination or in real situation. While Barnes (2009) describes art as the product of creative human activity in which materials are shaped or selected to convey an idea, emotion or visually interesting forms to the viewer.

Art means different things to different reasons depending on the perception of the concept by the individual concerned. In his own definition of the concept, Uzoagba (2000:2) states that art is a human conception made manifest by the skillful use of a medium. Not until man executes the kind of art in his mind, what he has in his mind can be predicted. It signifies a doing, a making, a fashioning or putting together, and it usually implies that the thing is accomplished by human skill. Aniakor (1982) believes that no matter what the definition of art is, it must derive its vitality from the internal dynamic of the

society to which it belongs. Art as society identity is perceived from the services it renders from time to time in such society.

However, Lazzari and Schlesier (2008:4) observe that "no definitions are universal, timeless and absolute. All definitions are framed within larger systems of knowledge and these systems shift and evolve". A definition that is acceptable in one culture may be rejected in another, hence art differs with culture. For instance, the culture of Africa which reflects in their art can never be the same with the art of the West, (European art).

This recalls the view of one school of thought called the Aestheticians towards art. They have earlier disagreed about proper definition of art. Howbeit, they seem to share a conviction that artistic experience involves two basic modes of participation, that is, "expression through art" and "response to art".

According to Okoli (2006) Expression through art refers to the ideas and feeling that are conveyed by works of art. This involves:

1. The discovery of ideas: Ideas are discovered by meditations, through brain storming. This produces a mental picture of an issue.
2. Transformation of the ideas by artistic means: Taking the ideas into drawing board. This is achieved through sketches and drawings.
3. Rendition of the ideas in an artistic medium: This is the execution of the real art work of choice of any medium.

Then, the experience which is evoked when an individual views a work of art is response. Therefore, response to the works of art involves:

1. Description of the works of art
2. Interpretation of the works of art and
3. Judgment of the works of art.

Although Sheldon Cheney describe? art as "the formal expression of a conceived image or imagined conception in terms of a given medium" (Ocvirk et al, 2006:4). Art is strictly a human phenomenon. Only human beings make art to communicate passions or ideas to others. It is primarily visual medium that is used to express ideas about our human experience and the world around us.

Who Is An Artist?

Artist: Artist is someone who creates art or produces works of art, especially paintings and sculptures. According to Lassari and Schlesier (2008:101), artists are creative people with exceptional skills who take meaningful ideas and embody them in visual form. This means that, artist expresses his ideas in a visual language. Visual language does not require interpretation before understanding it. For instance, when artist use paint to create his feelings (ideas) in the manner that affects the sense of beauty, the beautiful painted work does not required a second observation to be accepted as a work of an artist. Becoming an artist as Weintruab states has profound effect upon the quality and diversity of skills needed to function as one, Weintruab (2007:10). He perseveres in his actions of art production.

What is the attitude of an artist in Art Practice?

Attitude: Attitude as a concept has defiled many attempts by authors to clarify it. However, Micropedia Britannica (2005) presents the concept of attitude as arising from attempt to account for observed regularities in the behaviour of individual persons. The quality of one's attitude is judged from the observable, evaluative responses he tends to make. The way one behaves towards something or somebody that shows how he or she thinks or feels constitutes that person's attitude. Keith Harrell in his book "Attitude is everything" sees attitude to be paramount in achieving personal fulfillment. According to him a positive attitude is the foundation of a successful life. Attitude is everything because it is involved in everything we do. Optimist (individuals with positive attitudes) are more .successful than similarly talented people with pessimistic or negative attitudes. Citing the work of a Psychologist, Martin Selgman of University /of Pennsylvania, Keith Harrell (2005) stated that the former's research indicates that

negative attitudes can be changed to positive attitudes. To put positive attitude into action requires commitment, hard work and continuous effort. Attitude affects everything you do both personally and professionally. You should note that your attitude reflects you.

Reasons Why Nigerian Artists and Drop out of Practice

Artists and designers abandon professional practice due to personal, parental, societal and governmental factors. The drop out pattern is often connected of lack of an enabling environmental for the practice of art and design in Nigeria, This is perhaps why artists and Lack of Support from Government and Institutions.

Over the years, government and Institutions in Nigeria have not been clearly seen to support art practices. For example, artists and designers who have found themselves in die corridors of power In 'Nigeria have insisted that government policy on estate development arid construction of public buildings should encourage the use of art works in the form of sculptures, mural decorations, and other interior decorations. This aspect of construction policy was adopted in principle but abandoned For government collaboration with contractors, who appeared to have absolute distaste for art works and who interpreted public art to mean additional additional financial responsibilities of contractual estimate agreements. By this single art. Patronage for the artists was downplayed. A cultural policy for the encouragement of art and design was also formulated in the Cultural Policy for Nigeria (1999) in section 6.4 which states m sub-section (S.4.5 that: the state shall establish a National Gallery of Art whose objectives shall be:

- (a) to serve as repository for artistic creations and practices since the birth of the country -as a nation,
- (b) to promote creative yen ins in Nigerian artists and designers, and (e) to promote research., art education arid appreciation.

Unfortunately, some of these policies were never positively implemented 10 affect the lives of practicing artists,

Inadequate Career Guidance

Another factor among the list is counseling problems. Counseling is foundational and fundamental to any choice to be made or any step to be taken. Before anyone can be considered a dropout in a school he/she must have enrolled and later renounced schooling. So it is in careers such as art and design; the individual must have received professional training (or still receiving training) before quitting. It is not unlikely that he/she entered into it wrongly or that there was frustration along the line which might have led to lack of continuous interest. Guidance and counseling are very necessary before the choice of a career so as to be aware of what it takes to live an artist's life. Career counseling at the primary and secondary school levels could assist in making career discoveries that may benefit youths to choose an art career path that would enable Nigerian society to acquire a creative cultural workforce. This would support the growth of dedicated individuals in the economic growth of the nation.

Anidugbe (2003) suggests that modern artists and emerging art profession in Nigeria should be properly counseled to consider a number of issues crucial in their practice. One of them is experimentation and the courage to incorporate new ideas. Another is to possibly attain post-graduation training to enable work with new media and modern technology using local contents. Contrary to this, new entrants do not have sufficient aptitude and interest which would serve as a springboard and prerequisite for entering into remaining in the art profession. Awareness of the prospects and challenges of the profession is as important as the profession itself. Artists and designers can be made but the truth is that proper counseling before taking up a specialization is necessary to expose possible candidates to the nitty-gritty, prospects and challenges, as well as what it takes to start, cope, and prosper in the profession. Experience has shown that sufficient aptitude, interest and adequate funding are important factors to be clearly understood and considered.

Loosing hope of a Viable living

The economic gains in the practice of art do not seem to come by just as any other profession. The artist patiently completes his work in the studio, organizes exhibitions and waits on patrons and buyers. The

lack of adequate patronage for art and design products constantly dashes the hopes and aspirations of artists. The frustration which arises as a result of low patronage and sales of art works seem to have been a sufficient factor for the lack of perseverance on the part of professionals who drop out of practice as soon as their targets are not met. For example, some financial benefits are expected after exhibitions, yet many exhibitions may not have attracted good patronage and thus few artworks are sold. Practicing artists seem to depend on patronage which only comes by sometimes luck and the ability to influence patrons.

Wrong Priorities and Notions

Most youths are usually misguided to make up their priorities. The notion that the quicker and easiest way to make money is to push one's profession to one side and participate in active politics seems to be a wrong induction. Politics in Nigeria seem to be bedeviled by lavish lifestyles encouraged by huge capital votes released monthly by the federal government to politicians as wages and allowances. This splendor encourages youths in Nigeria to abandon their professional callings and identify themselves with political parties that can elevate them to elective posts where money will come by easily. There are records of trained artists who deviated to other professions which they thought would provide greater income than when in art practice. The record of rates of drop-out artists can be streamlined by standardization of formation and implementation of educational planning that will admonish cultural orientation in curricula and school syllabi. The use of art to create a focused cultural value system and the engagement of art in providing simulation for the reproduction in the industry is envisaged by this re-orientation. The 6-3-3-4 system of education in Nigeria should also be re-designed to foster the essentials of crafts in the service of mankind. This Nigerian system of education is a complete schooling system which is segmented into the first six years for the primary school education of the child. The next three years is for the Junior Secondary School. the last four years is meant to be spent to acquire tertiary education. The 4-year tertiary school system should consolidate the training by providing specialists education to all the branches of art.

Lack of Take-off Capital

The skit to practice art has not been a major problem of most creative artists and designers but the problem is a lack of capital. Undoubtedly, getting into full time private practice in Nigeria is capital intensive, it involves putting in place a space as studio or workshop, materials, accessorial facilities, and equipment. Despite having these necessary items, there is the need for an initial working capital that will take care of the day-to-day running of the studio and other miscellaneous spending. Many of the artists and designers who want to set up their private studios cannot do so because of the high cost involved particularly since finances still remain the backbone and livewire of every business. To help the situation, suggestions on methods of raising capital for professional private practice in Nigeria have been given in Kayode (2004). The methods are acquisition of loans from the appropriate financial institutions such as soliciting for support from government institutions such as the Accelerated Poverty Alleviation Agency (APAA) initiated by President Olusegun Obasanjo's civilian regime. The APAA was specially created by the government to assist the artisans and job seekers to obtain minimum loans. Other sources include the leasing of family inheritance of land and other properties. Personal effects and family inheritances as well as landed properties can be sold among the Yorubas of the southwestern Nigerian to start a business or sponsor children in schools. This is not a strange practice in Nigeria as a whole. For instance, parents who cherish and value education (formal and informal) as the best legacy they could bequeath to their children and kinsmen can afford to fall back on this option as a last resort.

Professional Practice in Art

Art and design practice are diverse activities which constantly attract debate as to the nature of their discipline and the role of the artist/designer (Swindells et al, 2001). Julier (2001), notes that despite successive government's attempts to make art and design.

Practicing art, craft, and design could suffice to becoming a profitable occupation in Nigeria if supported by some measure of patronage. Three categories of practitioners exist within the circle of the visual art

industry in Nigeria. The first being those who engage in full time practice. Full time designers and artists can be academic or non-academic. Either of them need be well organized or be situated in offices. This does not matter as the substance patronage pattern and propaganda of the individual will assist to sell name and work. Apart from mass producing works for sale through galleries, craft shops, trade fairs, and other retail outlets at minimal rate, a professional artist, designer, or those working as craftsman may sometimes have the opportunity of working on commission. This, according to Lowry (1997), means being asked to create a new piece of work for a specific client who may be an individual or organization that is fully committed to professional practice. The artist is established and organized to work for himself and produces volume of works (which could be prints, paintings, garments and fashion wares, pottery, glassware, leatherworks, jewelries, or sculptures) to be exhibited and sold to buyers. Buyers constitute the art patrons, private individuals, government and organizations like financial institutions, oil companies and agencies, as well as expatriate-collectors who acquire designs and art works either for sales or for utilization purposes. A full time professional artist/designer goes into a full time private professional practice with the intention to survive and live a fulfilled life under the employment of no one. The second category of art practitioners are those who are not self-employed but are working in art or design related employment. They are trained practitioners in their chosen fields of fine and applied arts and are engaged by organizations that rate them according to their skills or academic qualifications. This, by implication means that only those who have read or specialized in graphic design-related disciplines would be relevant in advertising, printing, and publishing or the television industry. Graduates who specialize in textiles could be engaged in textile, fashion and garment industries like Afrprint, Bobjson Seven Stars Industries, or Aswani Textiles (all located in Nigeria), while painters, and ceramic designers as well as other art specialists would find work in place where they were professionally relevant. The third category represents those working in the academic institutions (primary, secondary and tertiary schools), and teaching the visual arts to students. In Nigeria today, holders of Teaches Grade II Certificate (TC) are no longer employed to teach in the primary school system while those already in the system have been mandated to enroll for academic certificate programme higher than the TC Grade II. The minimum teaching qualification for primary school art teaching is the Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE). There are however, holders of universally degrees in the primary school teaching service as well.

Clearance Call

The way to move for art profession forward and must be clearly specified out in practical terms. The art and design bodies in Nigeria have a big stake in this regard, and the professional bodies such as the Society of Nigerian Artists (NSA), the Nigerian Society of Education through Art (NSEA), the Osogbo Group of Artists, and the Association of African Industries Designers (AAID) to mention but a few, used to operate by their various constitutions and were recognized by their artists activities. But today, those that can be regarded as functioning art and design associations in the country are the SNA, the Culture and Creative Art Forum (CCAF), and the Pan African Circle of Artists (PACA).

RECOMMENDATIONS

To redeem those anomalies, the art association in the country should be committed to encouraging professional qualification of both old and new members. The associations should make efforts to be upgraded to professional bodies and seek proper accreditation from the Nigerian government to be able to register, regulate practices, and award professional qualifications. This practice may not be actualized unless and until the art groups in Nigeria organize themselves into sub-groups to resist patrons' arrogance and dictators through sensitization. There is nothing wrong when an organization seeks loans from the government in sub-groups to foster trades and professions since the money for loans and advances belong to the nations. After all, artists and designers are bona fide members of the country. The associations should standardise and upgrade their credentials as well as develop proposals and strategies

for the beautification of the country as a nation. "When, recognitions are teamed, all; other problems such as low patronage, empathy, and the drop out syndrome may be drastically minimized.

Job Prospects for Artists

Visual artists, who never practiced art' and those who went into practice and later opted out could, be regarded as "Art Dropouts." The various art schools in Nigeria, academic and non-academic, have witnessed tremendous enrolment and graduation of students in the various areas of art; however, most of them after complementing and graduating as artists and designers seek jobs outside the field. Various studies have revealed that other professions are employing trained artists and designers as staff. Trained artists take up these jobs with the belief that white collar jobs muster attractive pay packages that are absent in art-related professions in the country. For example, there are many graduates of fine and applied arts who took up jobs in the Apapa Wharf Dock Yard in Lagos as passage and security officers. Some artists serve in active politics, while others are visual artists who never practiced, art and those who went into practice and later opted out: could be regarded as "Art Dropouts." The various art schools in Nigeria academic and non-academic have witnessed, tremendous enrolment and graduation of students, in the various areas of art; however, most of them, after completing and graduating as- artists and designers seek jobs outside the field.

Famous practicing artists in Nigeria include Bruce Onobrakpaye, David Dale, Yuruf Grillo, Olakunle Filani. Tola Wewe to mention but a few. Other emerging practicing artists who have made their mark at the exhibition grounds in Nigeria are mostly new entrants. Art patronage in Nigeria is all about getting the right connections in business organizations or in the "corridor of power" (Ojo, 2004), while other great talents wallow in abject poverty because of lack of exposure and connections, artists with little zeal swim in affluence and wealth because patronage in the Nigerian art market is about knowing the right people (e.g politicians, bureaucrats, directors and and key figures in various large organizations.

The non-famous artists is thus perceived as the one who does not have the right connections to showcase and attract patrons for his works. Fame in art, as it is in the Nigerian context can be induced by politics and mere propaganda. Sympathy is given to non-famous but talented artists who possess no enormous power and financial incentives. Educators and arts organizations are expected to influence Nigerian policy makers to find lasting solutions to this problem. This could be done when "protection for right of practice is guaranteed by governments at various levels where stipends and beautification contracts are awarded only to registered artist.

CONCLUSION

This paper has attempted to identify some causes and the seeming implications of artists and designers' attrition in Nigerian Exemplary lives of great Nigerian artists such as Bruce Onobrakpeya, David Dale, Kolade Osinowo, Abayomi Berber, and a host of others should be emulated by budding artists and designers in Nigeria. The great Nigerian artists started their practice from scratch and set outstanding records by training, mentoring and multiplying the number of artists in the country. A fundamental question is the consequences of the existence of great masters in Nigerian art practices. As great artists, designers, and craftsmen drop out of the profession for imagined greener pastures, it is envisaged that tough times are ahead in art practices in Nigeria. As suggested in this paper. The succor lies in the reform of artists and designers' societies such that can make them form formidable and legitimate forces to re-group to undertake public commissions.

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